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Effect of Seed Priming on Seed Germinability and Seedling Performance of Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*)

Author's Details:

Oyekale, K. O, Erumaka, J, Shobo, B. A, Oyekale, O. O.

Department of Agriculture and Industrial Technology, School of Science and Technology Babcock University
Ilishan-Remo, Nigeria

Corresponding e-mail: oyekalek@babcock.edu.ng

Abstract

The experiment was conducted at the horticultural unit of Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State. The main objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of priming on the agronomic performance of tomato. The study consisted of 4 treatments: 40g of NaCl per 1litre of water, 20g of NaCl per 1litre of water, 10g of NaCl per 1litre of water and 0g per 1litre of water (control). The tomato variety used was a local variety (NGB OO713). Each treatment was replicated four times. 100 grammes of tomato seeds was soaked in 1 litre of water diluted with the specified concentrations of NaCl according to treatments. The primed seeds were thereafter sowed in plastic containers filled with top soil, and the following agronomic data were taken at respective interval: Germination %, Seedling length (cm), Number of leaves per plant, Stem girth (cm), Root length, Seedling vigour index, Speed of germination. Analysis of Variance, Means separation and correlation analyses were carried out on the data obtained. Results showed that the treatment was not significant for all the seed viability and seedling vigour parameters evaluated. Some of the treatments however showed statistical differences. Positively significant correlations were recorded for most of the parameters, indicating a strong relationship. This study posited that all the NaCl concentrations used were not effective on the primed tomato seeds; which could indicate use of less than required concentration needed to properly condition the seeds. It is therefore recommended that further studies could consider increasing the salt concentration beyond 40 grammes for tomato seed priming

Keywords: Seed Priming, Seed Germinability, Seedling Performance, Field Establishment.

Introduction

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill) exhibits medicinal qualities as evident in its flavonoid, carotenoids, Vit. A, Xanthins, lutein, Vit. C and potassium contents (Afolayan *et al.*, (2014). However, Nigeria ranked the 13th among the fifteen top countries accounting for 1.7% of the world index (FAO, (2010); Shankara *et al.*, (2005). Strikingly, tomato production in Nigeria appears very low in terms of yield per hectare (20 t/ha) (Balarabe, 2012) compared with Brazil (60.7 t/ha), China (48.1 t/ha), USA (81.0 t/ha) and Italy (50.7 t/ha).

Seeds of some vegetable crops have been discovered to have innate dormancy. This makes germination and seedling emergence difficult, until the chemical composition of such seeds viz-a-viz the seed physiology is altered. If this problem is left unresolved, there is no guarantee of uniform seed germination and subsequent field establishment. The ultimate effect of this phenomenon is scanty plant population and eventual low yield and overall crop productivity. This, of course should not be left unattended to; thereby paving the way for the current study.

Seed priming improves seeds germination, seedlings vigor and plant performance. Over the past 20 years, a large number of studies confirmed that various seed pre-treatments triggering the so-called "pre-germinative metabolism" (Paparella and Araujo, 2006) have been used to improve seeds germination and yield (Badek and VanDuijin *et al.*, (2015), Horrii and McCue *et al.*, (2007). Obtaining vigorous seedlings and plants is the major premise for having a high crop yield of superior quality. The beneficial effects of seed pretreatment are not only reflected in the outcome of the germination process. To be more specific, seed priming is not only beneficial under normal culture conditions, but is also an appropriate means for the plant to successfully

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overcome the activities of stressors. Numerous studies have focused on other priming methods such as osmopriming, salinity priming, hormonal priming, and chemical priming. Studies carried out by T. S. Lara and J. M. S. Lira emphasized that tomato seeds priming with a solution of potassium nitrate (KNO₃) (50 mM) resulted in an increased germination time and rate compared to other treatments (i.e. polyethylene glycol (PEG 6000)).

Among different abiotic stress factors, salinity is one of the most important in many arid and semiarid regions. Salinity has a negative impact from the initial stages of seed germination and seedling growth and ultimately affects all the physiological and biochemical processes in a mature plant (Nawaz and Amjad 2012). Chen and Arora (2013), summarized two priming strategies to improve seed stress tolerance, with one ensuring an advanced status of the germination and the second providing a priming-induced 'stress imprint'. So far, numerous research approaches have been aimed at improving crop growth and development. For instance, many priming solutions have been previously tested and used such as hydropriming, osmopriming, solid matrix priming, biopriming, chemopriming, nutripriming, thermopriming etc. These techniques are generally easy to apply and the results are generally very positive. Seed priming with natural and/or synthetic compounds is a physiological seed enhancement method for overcoming poor and erratic seed germination. Regarding the germination rate of tomato seeds after priming with sodium chloride (NaCl) and gibberellic acid (GA), Nakaune and Hanada, (2012) reported values of 4.9 and 4.6 times higher at 36 hours after sowing compared to hydroprimed seeds, with endogenous abscisic acid levels being similar after sowing. These results suggest that the effect of NaCl is caused by an increase of the GA₄ content via GA biosynthetic genes activation, and a subsequent increase in the expression of genes related to endosperm cap weakening. In addition, osmopriming of tomato seeds in 10% (w/v) polyethylene glycol (PEG) solution for 2 days at 20±1°C in the dark followed by exposure at 25±1°C for 7 days under normal (water) and 100 mM NaCl conditions, respectively, showed that seeds germination could be improved under aging and salinity conditions. The main objective of this study was therefore to evaluate the effect of priming on the germinability and agronomic performance of tomato.

Materials and Method

Location of the Experiment

The experiment was conducted at the horticultural unit of Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State. A tomato variety (NGB 00713), sourced from National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB) was used.

Treatment formulation and application

Four levels of NaCl concentration were used. They are:

1. 40g of NaCl per 1litre of water
2. 20g of NaCl per 1litre of water
3. 10g of NaCl per 1litre of water
4. 0g per 1litre of water (control)

Seedlings were raised and maintained in the screen house for 4 weeks. Experimental materials used include; Seeds, Plastic containers, Water, Soil (top soil), Ruler, Vernier caliper, tape, 1-litre bottles, Petri dishes and filter paper.

The plastic containers were used as materials for holding the soil medium, water and salt (NaCl) were used as priming agents, the soil serves as medium of growth whereby the seeds were sown, the ruler will be used for linear measurements, the vernier caliper was used to measure or ascertain the stem girth of the plant, the paper tape was used to label the experimental containers in order to differentiate the replicated treatments, 1 litre

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bottles were used as priming chamber, the petri dishes and filter papers were used for the viability and vigour tests.

Evaluation

One hundred tomato seeds were soaked in sodium chloride (NaCl) concentration or water as applicable for 24hrs. After that, the water was drained and the seeds were air dried. Viability test was conducted to ensure the seeds are in good conditions before planting. The pots were arranged and labelled accordingly from 0g of NaCl (control) to 40g of NaCl in the the nursery. The experiment consisted of 4 treatments which were 0g of NaCl (control), 10g of NaCl, 20g of NaCl, 40g of NaCl and each of the treatments were replicated 4 times thereby making a total number of 16 pots or containers. Each of the pots had a total of 25 seeds planted in them with 4 replicates making a total of 100 seeds for each replicated treatment. After 7 days of planting the first seedling emergence occurs. In the nursery at 4 and 6 weeks after planting, agronomic data on the tomato seedlings were taken, and this included; Germination percentage, Seedling length (cm), Number of leaves per plant, Stem girth (cm), Root length, Seedling vigour index, Speed of germination.

The data collected were subjected to Analysis of variance (ANOVA), to determine if the treatments were significant (at 5% and 1% levels of probability) for the agronomic parameters evaluated. Significant means were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test at 5% probability level; and correlation analysis was also carried out to determine relationships among the seed viability and seedling vigour characters.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the treatments had no significant effect on all variables measured at four weeks after planting. This phenomenon is probably because the plants are still growing and their agronomic characteristics are not yet properly established. Results in Table 2 also followed similar trend as in Table 1. There was no significant effect of treatment on all variables measured at 6 weeks after planting. This could be as a result of low sodium chloride as a priming agent in the tomato seeds. Decreasing germination percent by the effect of low salt concentration is in consistence with the result of Xiao-Fang *et al.* (2000). Table 3 shows that root length at 4 weeks, seedling length at 4 weeks and stem girth at 4 weeks are not significantly different along the column according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test, but number of leaves per plant at 4 weeks and percent germination are significantly different. The highest value is at 4 weeks after planting for 20g of NaCl (26.2500) and the lowest is 40g of NaCl (1.5600), percent germination shows similar trend in priming of tomato seeds with NaCl which causes a sort of increase in percent germination and rapid establishment of seedlings from treated seeds (Demir Kaya *et al*; 2006; Foti *et al*; 2008). The results on tomato seedling length (cm) are presented in table 4 at 6 weeks after planting (WAP). In table 4 there are 4 treatments with 5 parameters. Data were taken on the seedling length at 6 weeks, the seedling length indexed by height increased with age, irrespective of treatments. However, significantly taller or shorter seedling length ($p > 0.05$) were recorded during the course of the experiment at 6 weeks after planting (WAP). Data on the stem girth at 6 weeks shows that 40g of NaCl (0.0925) shows lower value than the 20g of NaCl (0.1700). Data on the number of leaves per plant at 6 weeks shows that 20g of NaCl (28.0000) showed more response sodium chloride having more leave number making it have a significantly more profuse foliage compared to 40g of NaCl (11.0000) table 4, nevertheless increased plant foliage was observed with age irrespective of the priming treatments at different levels of concentrations. Profuse leaf production is an apparent index of the plant's ability for enhanced production of photosynthates by the process of photosynthesis. The effect of priming using NaCl on seedling length at 6 weeks on tomato seeds at control, 10g of NaCl, 20g of NaCl, and 40g of NaCl had no significant difference (table 4). This shows that priming at 40g of NaCl does not affect seedling length. The stem girth at 6 weeks has significant difference i.e there was an increment on the stem girth compared to table 3 at 4 weeks, number of leaves (per plant) at 6 weeks shows no significant difference (table 4), this shows that at priming at

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40g of NaCl doesn't change number of leaves per plant. Seedling vigour shows no significant difference, speed of germination shows significant difference along the column.

Table 1. Means square from analysis of variance for five agronomic characters evaluated for primed tomato seeds at four weeks after planting.

Source	df	seedl at 4wks	steng at 4wks	noofl at 4wks	SVI	Percentgerm
Trt	3	6.916 ^{ns}	18.643 ^{ns}	3.916 ^{ns}	1235.871 ^{ns}	776.600 ^{ns}

Key: Trt (treatment), Rep (replication), seedl (seedling length), steng (stem girth), noofl (Number of leaves per plant), SVI (seedling vigour index), Percentgerm (percent germination).

Table 2. Mean square from analysis of variance for five agronomic characters evaluated for primed tomato seeds at six weeks after planting.

Source	df	seedl at 6wks	steng at 6wks	noofl at 6wks	SVI	SOG
Trt	3	50.962 ^{ns}	0.14 ^{ns}	656.188 ^{ns}	99410.600 ^{ns}	3.401 ^{ns}

Key: Trt (Treatment), Seedl (seed length), Steng (Stem girth), noofl (number of leaves), SVI (Seedling vigour index), SOG (speed of germination).

Table 3. Means of five agronomic characters for four priming treatment of tomato seeds evaluated at four weeks after planting

Treatments	Rootl at 4wks	seedl at 4wks	steng at 4wks	noofl at 4wks	percent germ
Control	6.7000 ^a	0.1278 ^a	13.7500 ^{ab}	13.7500 ^{ab}	24.0000 ^a
10g of NaCl	4.10 00 ^a	5.1000 ^a	0.1375 ^a	11.500 ^{ab}	17.0000 ^{ab}
20g of NaCl	4.4250 ^a	7.1750 ^a	0.1325 ^a	26.2500 ^a	24.0000 ^a
40g of NaCl	3.1280 ^a	8.0750 ^a	1.2750 ^a	1.8600 ^b	7.0000 ^b

Key: Rootl (Root length), seedl (seedling length), steng (stem girth), noofl (Number of leaves per plant), percent germ (percent germination)

Table 4. Means of five agronomic traits for four priming treatments of tomato seeds evaluated at six weeks after planting.

Treatments	seedl at 6wks	steng at 6wks	noofl at 6wks	SVI	SOG
Control	9.9500 ^a	0.1560 ^{ab}	16.5000 ^a	209.7000 ^a	1.45750 ^{ab}
10g of NaCl	6.8500 ^a	0.1600 ^{ab}	14.2500 ^a	116.8000 ^a	1.0600 ^{ab}
20g of NaCl	8.8500 ^a	0.1700 ^a	28.0000 ^a	250.1000 ^a	1.5725 ^a

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40g of NaCl	5.3250 ^a	0.0925 ^b	11.0000 ^a	48.4000 ^a	0.3900 ^b
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Means on the same row followed by the same letter are significantly different according to duncan's multiple range test at 5% probability level.

Key: seedl (seedling length), stemg (stem girth), noofl (Number of leaves per plant), SVI (seedling vigour index), SOG (speed of germination).

The correlation analysis results at 4 weeks after planting between seedling length at 4 weeks and stem girth at 4 weeks shows that the two variables are positively and highly significantly correlated ($r = 0.794^{**}$) implying that more massive stem girth of tomato are the higher the seedling length. This can be explained with the knowledge that stem girth of tomato has a relationship site for seedling length initiation (Table 5). A similar result between number of leaves per plant at 4 weeks and percent germination shows a low but positively significant relationship ($r = 0.859^{**}$). The more percent germination the more the number of leaves induced per plant. Table 6 shows seedling length at 6 weeks and seedling vigour index are positively significant (0.748^{**}), that is seedling length has a relation with seedling vigour index. This is the same with seedling length and speed of germination, implying that the higher the speed of germination the rapid the growth in seedling length.

Table 5. Relationship among five agronomic traits of primed tomato seeds evaluated at six weeks after planting.

Rootl at 4wks	seedl at 4wks	stemg at 4wks	noofl at 4wks	percent germ
Rootl at 4wks	0.622 ^{ns}	0.321 ^{ns}	0.081 ^{ns}	0.380 ^{ns}
Seedl at 4wks		0.794 ^{**}	0.152 ^{ns}	0.265 ^{ns}
Stemg at 4wks			-0.287 ^{ns}	0.200 ^{ns}
Noofl at 4wks				0.859 ^{**}
<u>Percent germ</u>				

Key: Rootl (Root length), Seedl (seedling length), Stemg (stem girth), noofl (number of leaves per plant), percent germ (percent germination).

Table 6. Relationship among five agronomic traits of primed tomato seeds evaluated at six weeks after planting.

	Seedl at 6wks	stemg at 6wks	noofl at 6wks	SVI	SOG
Seedl at 6wks		0.610 ^{ns}	0.615 ^{ns}	0.741 ^{**}	0.671 ^{**}
Stemg at 6wks			0.680 ^{ns}	0.549 [*]	0.665 ^{**}
Noofl at 6wks				0.868 ^{**}	0.642 ^{**}
SVI					0.946 ^{**}
<u>SOG</u>					

Key: Seedl (seedling length), stemg (Stem girth), Noofl (Number of leaves per plant), SVI (Seedling vigour index), SOG (speed of germination).

Conclusion

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Pre-treatment of tomato seeds with NaCl accelerated some metabolic processes that triggered seed germination; though not at significantly effective level. The slightly higher growth performance of tomato from primed seeds seems to be as a result of higher capacity for osmotic adjustment owing to the fact that primed seeds have more Na⁺ and Cl⁻ in roots and more sugars and organic acids in leaves than seeds from non-primed seeds. It is obvious however from the results of this work that the concentration regime used might not be sufficient to trigger significant growth. It is recommended that higher concentration of sodium chloride should be used in priming of tomato seeds for better efficacy. This is due to the fact that priming at 40g of NaCl did not have significant effect. Further works should therefore concentrate on priming with NaCl at higher concentrations. This could probably give better responses in terms of improved seed viability and seedling vigour.

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